

Recruitment Process for Educators at Special Schools (SLB) Gorontalo City

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to study and find out how the recruitment process of teaching staff at the Gorontalo City Special School (SLB). The sub-focus in this study is the process of planning, implementation and placement. The research method used in this study is qualitative descriptive. While data collection uses observation, interview and secondary data recording techniques. In accordance with the type of research used, the data analysis technique used is a qualitative analysis technique. The results showed that from the aspect of planning, implementation and placement were not effective or did not support the Recruitment Process. The things suggested in this study are expected by local governments, especially the Education Office, to pay attention to obstacles that can hinder the recruitment process of teaching staff, especially in SKB, if this condition is allowed to continue and no solution is found, it will affect the quality of education in SKB Gorontalo City.

INTRODUCTION

One of the recruitment of teaching staff is not mature in planning to be in accordance with what is needed to be more effective and efficient according to the vision and mission of the school concerned. As a result, there are many teaching staff who are incompetent or in other words have no competence in subjects that are taught but are still forced to teach. Sekolah Luar Luar is the only school in Gorontalo City in carrying out the education and learning process supported by 61 educators or teachers, and 245 students.

Based on this, it can be seen from the special requirements, for example, general teachers can be accepted with the provision that they must have a certificate of special education skills, but in the process of recruiting educators, most prospective educators do not have the required certificates, so that the process of identifying subject areas that have been prepared in advance in schools is extraordinarily empty.

The recruitment of educators has not been maximally carried out, it can be seen from the need for educators needed is around 27 educators who have educational competencies and qualifications with special needs educational backgrounds, at least have certificates of special education skills such as deaf, mentally impaired, and mentally impaired, especially in special schools (SLB), but what is available or recruited so far is only educators who have general education qualifications, and do not yet have a certificate of special education skills.

Placement in the recruitment process of educators has not been maximally carried out, it can be shown from the recruitment implementation has not run according to the plan that has been previously set, such as educators who are not required according to school needs, for example recruiting art teachers only based on the experience and talents of the applicant not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant. This happens because the placement carried out by related agencies, in this case, the Gorontalo City Education Office is less effective.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Public Administration

According to Syafiie (2014: 17) the term public comes from English *public* which means general, community or state. Actually, in Indonesian appropriate when given a *praja* translation, only since Dutch times have the Sanskrit words been misunderstood. The true meaning of the word *praja* is the people, so that for the government that serves the needs of all people is given the term *pamong praja* (servant of the people).

According to Nawawi (in Syafii, 2014: 13: 14) administration is an activity or series of activities as a process of controlling the cooperation efforts of a group of humans to achieve common goals that have been set previously. According to Pasolong (2013: 3) from some of these definitions, it can be formulated that administration is a planned work carried out by a group of people in collaboration to achieve goals on an effective, efficient and rational basis.

According to Chandler in Pasolong (2013: 7) said that public administration is a process in which public power and personnel are organized and coordinated to formulate, implement, and *manage* decisions in public policy. From some of the definitions of public administration above, the author can provide an understanding that public administration is an administration that is assembled in a government and private organization by realizing the achievement of the goals of the organization.

Management

Manullang (2012: 5), defines management as "the process of activities from a leader (manager) that must be carried out using scientific and practical methods, to achieve predetermined goals, through the cooperation of other people as a source of labor and by utilizing the resources available for it in an appropriate way". Hasibuan (2016:5) defines that management is: "a process of activities carried out through a cooperation carried out by several people or together with others to achieve the desired goals of the organization". Then Follet (in Handoko, 2014: 3) gives the understanding that "management is the art of completing work through others".

Based on the above opinion, it can be concluded that in terms of management contains the core among others: Management is a combination of science and art. Management is a systematic, coordinated and cooperative process in an effort to utilize all available resources. Management has certain goals, the success of these goals depends on the ability to utilize all existing potential. Management functions according to Winardi, (2012: 161) include the following: a). *Planning*, b). *Organizing*, c). *Directing*, d). *Controlling*.

Policy Implementation

Van Matter and Van Horn (in Wahab, 2014: 60) define policy implementation as: "Actions carried out by the public or private individually or in groups aimed at achieving predetermined goals, in *policy decisions*" In Grindle's opinion (in Wibawa, 2012: 24) the entire process of implementing a new policy begins when the objectives of the originally general objectives have been met, an action program has been designed and some funds / costs have been allocated to realize these goals and objectives.

Furthermore, Grindle (in Wibawa, 201: 2: 22) argues that to analyze the success of policy implementation can be seen in the content and context of the policy. This study looks at the three dimensions of analysis in organizations, namely goals, task implementation, and organizational relationships with the environment. The content of the policy includes: 1). Interests affected by the policy; 2). The type of benefit to be generated; 3). The desired degree of change ; 4). The position of policy makers; 5). Program Implementer; and 6). Resources involved. The policy context includes: 1). The power, interests and strategies of the actors involved; 2). Characteristics of institutions and rulers and; 3). Decision and responsiveness of the implementer.

Human Resource Management

Personnel management is planning, organizing, directing, supervising procurement activities, developing, compensating, integrating, maintaining employees or employees in order to achieve individual, organizational, and community goals. The statement from Flippo equates the understanding of human resource management with personnel management. Winardi, (2012: 65) said that human resource management has various tasks related to efforts to have, train, develop, motivate, organize, and maintain company employees

Simamora (in Sanusi, 2012) suggests that HRM focuses its discussion on organizing human resources (HR). The main task of HRM is to manage the human element both through the *leadership process* in order to obtain HR performance in carrying out its functions and duties in the organization.

1. Human Resource Procurement
2. Human Resource Development
3. Human Resource Evaluation

Recruitment

Bernardine R. Wirjana (2021: 55), explained "Recruitment is a process to find potential applicants to fill real or anticipated vacancies". According to Hasibuan (2016: 174), *recruitment* is an activity to find and influence workers to apply for vacant job vacancies in companies or agencies "Seeking is determining the sources of labor to be withdrawn and influencing is determining the ways of withdrawal, such as through advertisements in mass media or through existing employees / employees".

According to Sondang P. Siagian (2015: 102), argues "Recruitment is the process of finding, finding and attracting capable applicants to be employed in and by an organization". According to Hasibuan (2016: 174), *recruitment* is an activity to find and influence workers to apply for vacant job vacancies in companies or agencies "Seeking is determining the sources of labor to be withdrawn and influencing is determining the ways of withdrawal, such as through advertisements in the mass media or through existing employees / employees.

Based on the foregoing, recruitment or withdrawal of labor is needed to screen applicants who want to apply. In organizations, recruitment is one of the important processes in determining whether or not applicants will apply to the organization.

Recruitment Process

The recruitment process can be described as follows:

- 1) Planning
Recruitment Planning is essentially a process of determining and attracting applicants who are able to work in a company (Rivai & Sagala, 2016: 148).
- 2) Implementation
After the recruitment plan is set, it then becomes the task of the HR manager to carry out recruitment or think of some recruitment alternatives that are usually done by companies at the most efficient cost. The need for this alternative. The purpose of recruitment is to receive as many applicants

as possible in accordance with the qualifications needed by the company from various sources of applicants, so that it will be possible to capture prospective employees of the highest quality and best (Rivai & Sagala, 2016: 150).

3) Placement

Placement is a follow-up to selection, namely placing prospective employees who are accepted (pass the selection) in positions / jobs that need it and delegate authority to that person (Hasibuan 2016: 98).

Educators

Law of the Republic of Indonesia No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers means that teachers are educators with the main task of educating, teaching, guiding, directing, training, assessing and evaluating students in early childhood education formal education pathways, primary education and secondary education.

Zakiah Daradjat (2012: 67) defines the word teacher as a professional educator, because implicitly he has given up accepting and shouldering some of the educational responsibilities carried on the shoulders of parents. According to Marimba (2012: 43) Teachers are people who have the responsibility to educate. Meanwhile, according to Hadari Nawawi quoted by Abuddin Nata (2014: 39) said that teachers are people whose work is to teach or provide lessons at school. Meanwhile, in his opinion, Sutari Imam Barnadib quoted by Hery Noer Aly (2015: 63) said a teacher is everyone who deliberately influences others to reach maturity.

Figure 1. Research Conceptual Framework

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive type of qualitative approach. Descriptive research qualitative approach, according to Bogdan and Taylor (in Moleong, 2018: 3), as a research procedure that produces descriptive data in the form of written or spoken words from people from observable behavior. This research was conducted at the Special School (SLB) Gorontalo City. The focus of research is the recruitment process of educators is conceptualized as a process of developing human resources which will be seen from the planning, implementation, and placement that are operationalized.

Data sources in this study are: a). Primary data are data obtained from informants, namely Principal 1 (one) person, Vice Principal 1 (one) person, Head of Sub Division of Personnel 1 (one) person, Head of Administration 1 (one) person, educators / teachers 3 (three) people. The total number of informants is 7

(seven) people. b). Secondary data is available data that can be used as a supporting basis in analyzing problems related to this research. Data Collection Techniques are Observation, Interview, and Documentation. Data analysis in this study is qualitative descriptive analysis consisting of several stages, namely: a). Data reduction, b). Data Presentation, c). Conclusion Drawing.

RESULTS

Planning

The planning referred to in this study is the process of activities or the preparation of the required activity steps in accordance with the rules for recruitment of educators, namely recruiting educators who have special knowledge educational backgrounds in extraordinary schools so that the recruitment of educators is according to the plan that has been set. The results of an interview with a key informant (YA) as the Principal said that

"We have done teacher planning according to the needs of special schools, namely specially educated teachers, and we do that almost every year. Then we submit the results of the teacher needs analysis to the Office through the Head of the Sub-Division of Personnel of the Education and Culture Office for follow-up and as a basis for the recruitment process for educators or teachers at SLB Negeri Kota Gorontalo." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of the interview with the informant (IP) as the Vice Principal said that:

"So far, we, from the school through the principal of SKB Gorontalo City, have planned the needs of teachers or educators, especially educators or teachers with special education. Because SLB schools really need these teachers. Because teachers or educators with special education in SLB Gorontalo City are very lacking, there are only 8 people out of 64 teachers in SLB." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of the interview with the informant (NKH) as the Head of the Sub-Division of Personnel stated that:

"My observation so far, that Gorontalo City State Special School (SLB) always conducts teacher planning according to the needs of extraordinary schools, namely special education teachers, and is carried out almost every year. Then it is sent to the Education Office through the Head of the Sub-Division of Personnel. From this proposal, it will be used as a basis by the Education and Culture Office to carry out a recruitment process for special education teachers." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of interviews with informants (ED) as teachers or educators stated that;

"From my observation so far, the Principal and his staff of the teacher council always hold meetings every year regarding the plan for teacher needs needed in Gorontalo City Special School (SLB). Because Special Schools (SLB) really need teachers, especially teachers in the field of study who are specially educated." (interview dated, May 23, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, it illustrates that Gorontslo City Special School (SLB) really needs teachers, especially teachers in the field of study who are specially educated. So that every year the Gorontalo City Special

School (SLB) conducts teacher planning according to the needs submitted to the Office to meet the needs of teachers or educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) which until now are considered still lacking. Based on several statements or interviews with informants, and according to observations, researchers show that the Recruitment Process of Educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) seen from the planning aspect has not been optimal or has not supported. This happens because the planning for the needs of teachers or educators carried out by SLB cannot be accommodated by the Office through the recruitment process carried out, because the department that is opened has no applicants or enthusiasts. Especially specially educated teachers. So that teachers or educators are considered still lacking in Gorontalo City State Special Schools (SLB).

Implementation

The implementation referred to in this study is the implementation of recruitment of educators carried out or adjusted to the needs of extraordinary schools based on initial planning, namely recruiting educators who have special education qualifications or at least educators have special education skills certificates. The results of interviews with key informants (YA) as the Principal said that:

"In my opinion, the recruitment of educators has been carried out, but it has not been optimally carried out. This can be seen from the educators or teachers recruited not in accordance with needs, where of the 64 educators in special schools, only about 27 education staff / teachers have special skill certificates, the others have not. Educators/teachers who have educational competencies and qualifications with special needs education backgrounds have not been met. (interview date, May 21, 2023).

The results of an interview with an informant (UD) as the Head of Administration said that:

"So far, the recruitment of educators has often been carried out, which is carried out almost every year, considering that Gorontalo City Special School (SLB) really needs teachers who have special needs education backgrounds who will teach students who are deaf, grahita, disabled, and visually impaired." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of the interview with the informant (NKH) as the Head of the Sub-Division of Personnel stated that:

"In my opinion, the recruitment of educators has been carried out, but the Education Office has not been able to grant or accommodate the proposal for the needs of educators submitted by the Special School (SLB), namely recruiting teachers who have educational competencies and qualifications who have a special needs education background, the Office has opened the formation of educators needed by SLB, but there is no registration or interest, so that the Department is forced to provide qualified educators." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of interviews with informants (IA) as teachers or educators stated that;

"My observation so far is that the recruitment for SLB teacher educators has been carried out and this is done by the Office based on the analysis of teacher needs submitted by Sekolah Lar Biasa (SLB). However, I consider that the recruitment has not been able to meet the needs of teachers in SLB, especially educators or teachers who have educational competencies and qualifications who have a special needs education background. So far, those recruited are educators or teachers with general education qualifications, to meet the available quota" (interview date, May 23, 2023).

Based on several statements or interviews with informants, and according to observations, researchers show that the Recruitment Process for Educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) seen from the implementation aspect has not been effective or has not supported. This happens because the recruitment process of educators carried out by the Office has not been able to provide the educators needed by Special Schools (SLB), namely those with special needs education backgrounds. The recruitment process carried out so far is more directed at educators or teachers who have competence or qualifications in general education, in order to meet the available quota.

Placement

The placement referred to in this study is to place educators into extraordinary schools based on school needs, namely educators who have educational qualifications or special education backgrounds, so that the implementation process is carried out in accordance with the provisions of the previously established plan.

The results of an interview with a key informant (YA) as the Principal said that

"The placement of educators or teachers is the full authority of the Education Office, so I as a leader in the Special School (SLB) consider that the placement is not in accordance with school expectations. This can be seen from educators or teachers who are placed less in accordance with the needs of special schools (SLB)." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of the interview with the informant (NKH) as the Head of the Sub-Division of Personnel stated that:

"The placement of educators or teachers in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) has been carried out. However, we admit that those placed have not been in accordance with the needs of special schools (SLB), namely educators or teachers who have educational competencies and qualifications who have a special needs education background. Because the formation of teachers who have special needs education backgrounds is not filled / empty. So that the Office only places educators or teachers who have competence or qualifications in general education at SLB Gorontalo City." (interview dated, May 21, 2023).

The results of interviews with informants (SYA) as teachers or educators stated that:

"My observation so far is that the placement of educators or teachers in Special Schools (SLB) has not been maximized. This can be seen from the educators or teachers placed by the Department less in accordance with the needs of the

school. For example, recruiting art teachers is based only on the experience and talents of the applicant, not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant." (interview dated, May 23, 2023).

From the informant's statement above, it shows that there is still recruitment of educators or teachers based only on the experience and talents of the applicant, not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant. This condition is certainly not in accordance with the planned needs of educators or teachers in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB).

Based on several statements or interviews with informants, and according to observations, researchers show that the Recruitment Process for Educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) seen from the placement aspect has not been maximized or has not supported. This happens because the educators or teachers who are placed are not in accordance with the needs of special schools (SLB). This can be shown from most of the teachers placed in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) have not been in accordance with the proposal from the results of the analysis of the needs of educators in schools submitted by Special Schools (SLB) to the Education Office. In addition, educators or teachers who are placed are only based on the experience and talents of the applicant, not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant.

DISCUSSION

The Recruitment Process of Educators in Special Schools (SLB) Gorontalo City, which is seen from the aspects of planning, implementation, and placement, has not been optimally carried out. In a planning spec studied in the research is the process of activities or the preparation of the required activity steps in accordance with the rules of recruitment of educators, namely recruiting educators who have special knowledgeable educational backgrounds in extraordinary schools so that the recruitment of educators is according to a predetermined plan. The results showed that the Recruitment Process of Educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) which was seen from the planning aspect was not optimal or had not supported. Because the planning for the needs of teachers or educators carried out by SLB cannot be accommodated by the Office through the recruitment process carried out, because the department that is opened has no applicants or applicants. Especially specially educated teachers. So that teachers or educators are considered still lacking in Gorontalo City State Special Schools (SLB). This result is consistent with what was stated by Simamora, (2015: 170) who said that planning as a series of activities to find and attract job applicants with the motivation, ability, expertise, and knowledge needed to cover the deficiencies identified in personnel planning. The result of recruitment is a group of job applicants who will be selected into new employees in the company. Included in the recruitment planning of educators needed by special schools.

The implementation aspect is one of the studies in this study, the implementation is a recruitment process for educators carried out or adjusted to

the needs of extraordinary schools based on initial planning, namely recruiting educators who have special education qualifications or at least educators have special education skills certificates. The results showed that the Recruitment Process of Educators in Special Schools (SLB) Gorontalo City which was seen from the implementation aspect has not been effective or has not supported. Because the recruitment process of educators carried out by the Office has not been able to provide the educators needed by Special Schools (SLB), namely those with special needs education backgrounds. The recruitment process carried out so far is more directed at educators or teachers who have competence or qualifications in general education, in order to meet the available quota. This result is consistent with what was stated by Rivai & Sagala, (2016: 150) which said that the purpose of recruitment is to accept as many applicants as possible in accordance with the qualifications needed by the company from various applicant sources, so that it will allow the highest and best quality prospective employees. This includes recruiting educators in accordance with the competencies or qualifications needed by extraordinary schools.

The placement aspect in this study is to place educators into extraordinary schools based on school needs, namely educators who have educational qualifications or special education backgrounds, so that the implementation process is carried out in accordance with the provisions of the previously established plan. The results showed that the Recruitment Process of Educators in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) which was seen from the placement aspect was not optimal or had not supported. This happens because the educators or teachers who are placed are not in accordance with the needs of special schools (SLB). This can be shown from most of the teachers placed in Gorontalo City Special Schools (SLB) have not been in accordance with the proposal from the results of the analysis of the needs of educators in schools submitted by Special Schools (SLB) to the Education Office. In addition, educators or teachers who are placed are only based on the experience and talents of the applicant, not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant. This result is consistent with what was stated by Hariandja (2015: 76) who said that placement is the process of assigning / filling positions or filling positions or reassigning employees to new tasks / positions or different positions. This assignment can be the first assignment for a newly hired employee, but it can also be through promotion, transfer, and demotion and even termination. Including the placement of educators or teachers based on the educational qualifications needed by special schools.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Processes of educator recruitment seen from the aspects of planning, implementation and placement have not been maximized or have not supported the recruitment of educators in extraordinary schools. Judging from the planning aspect, it has not been maximized, because the needs of teachers carried out through the analysis of the needs of educators or teachers by SLB have not been accommodated by the Office through the recruitment process carried out. Judging from the implementation aspect, it has not been effective,

because the recruitment process of educators carried out by the Office has not been able to provide the educators needed by Special Schools (SLB), namely those with special needs education backgrounds. Judging from the placement aspect, it has not been maximized, because the educators or teachers placed are only based on the experience and talents of the applicant, not based on the educational background or educational qualifications of the applicant. This condition is not in accordance with the needs of special schools (SLB). Therefore, the need for SKB in planning educators is carried out through an analysis of the needs of educators or teachers by involving the Head of the Sub-Division of Civil Service or Section for the procurement of employees or teachers in the Education Office. The need for SKB to map the needs of educators or teachers based on classes with disabilities. The need for SKB to coordinate intensively with the Education Office in the placement of educators or teachers.

FURTHER STUDY

In this study, researchers only looked at the recruitment process of teaching staff at the Gorontalo City Special School (SLB). The sub-focus in this study is the process of planning, implementation and placement. So that researchers hope that the next researcher will further increase the scope of the indicators studied so that the research results are of higher quality.

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